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Chrono Stability or Quantum Stability: Removing the Imaginary Component of Electronics

The imaginary component that appear in semiconductor electronics can be removed by

1. Celestial Positioning Encryption
2. Analog Firewalls
3. Total Analog Systems with just CPU or NPU at the center
4. Programmable Matter

Removing the imaginary component has a very high importance in life. Imaginary components say 'ib' in a 'a +ib' equation must be removed for Quantum Stability of the electronic system.

Details of each point are classified under SIU.

[Mohanty, S. \(2025\). Time: The released Arrow of Big Bang. Zenodo.](#)